

PRIME MINISTER OF TURKESTAN AUTONOMY

MUHAMMADJON TINISHBOEV`S LIFE AND ACTIVITY (1879-1931).

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Abstract. In the article, information about the life and activities of the prime minister of the Turkestan Autonomous Region, Muhammadjon Tinishboev, who occupied an important place in the history of Uzbek statehood, is covered based on archival sources.

Keywords. Autonomy, Jadids, Duma, Bolsheviks, archive, source.

The post of prime minister of the Turkestan Autonomy for a short period of time (November 28 - December 10, 1917) Muhammadjon Tinishboev's life and activities are considered to be one of the persons who should be studied in the history of our country. He is not only an engineer, but also a great politician, physicist and historian.

At the beginning of the 20th century, when the socio-political views of M. Tinishboev were just being formed, Kazakhstan was one of the backward colonial regions of the Russian Empire, and the socio-economic and political situation here was characterized by the aggravation of agrarian and national issues. The socio-political movement that arose in such conditions, while setting national-democratic tasks, also gave a great impetus to the political career of Kazakh intellectuals. Among them were Mustafa Chokai, Alikhan Bukeykhanov, Ahmad Boytursunov, Yaqub Akboev and, of course, Muhammadjon Tinishboev.

M. Tinishboev's political outlook was already formed during his studies in St. Petersburg in 1900-1906. For example, the report entitled "Kazakhs and Social

Movement" critically discussed the outdated system of governance in Kazakhstan and other colonial territories, the way of life of Kazakhs from the point of view of democracy.

The desire to see the motherland free and liberated prompted M. Tinishboev to gain experience as a public and political figure. This was especially evident in the elections to the first and second State Dumas. M. Tinishboev nominated from the Semirechensk region will start his career as a deputy in the Duma.

The nomination and election of M. Tinishboev's candidate testifies to the high prestige of the 28-year-old politician and engineer, and the people's trust in him. Although the second State Duma did not last long (it was dissolved on July 3, 1907), M. Tinishboev went down in history as a Kazakh deputy who criticized the agrarian policy of the government of the Russian Empire from its pulpit.

M. Tinishboev was a politician who openly announced his opinions not only from the high state pulpits, but also in the press. From 1913 to March 1918, he published many articles under the pseudonym "Kazakh Engineer" in the "Kazakh" newspaper, which operated in Orenburg.

After the February revolution of 1917 M. Tinishboev threw himself completely into political activity. He took part in the establishment of uezd and oblast Kazakh committees and worked as a member of the special Turkestan committee of the Provisional Government. At the same time, the Provisional Government. He was appointed the commissioner of Yettisuv region.

In 1916, when the national liberation movements were brutally suppressed by the Tsar's government, he carried out great work to return the emigrant Kazakhs and Kyrgyz from China to Etisuv.

The February Revolution of 1917 encouraged M. Tinishboev and all representatives of the Kazakh intelligentsia to become politically independent.

In this regard, the Council of All Kazakhs in Orenburg, held in June 1917, was of great importance. First, this council was an important impetus for the

establishment of Kazakh political parties. This accelerated political processes such as building an independent state and raising the political consciousness of the population. Secondly, it caused the development of all mechanisms (religion, science, education and court) on the way to democratization of society. Also, the council adopted the development program of the Alash party, which is important for the Kazakh people. This project consists of 10 points, in which concepts such as civil rights, science and enlightenment, and private property were placed.

In December 1917, the 2nd All-Kazakh Congress was held in Orenburg. It was decided to establish the Alash Horde state on the basis of the Provisional Government. 15 Kazakh state and public figures, as well as M. Tinishboev, were included in the government.

M. Tinishboev, on the one hand, led the strengthening of the "Alash" party, and on the other hand, the establishment of Turkestan Autonomy.

However, the termination of Turkestan Autonomy changed his plans. Therefore, on August 31, 1918, he organized a meeting with Kazakh politicians in Ettisuv to discuss the future of the Alash Horde state.

In the spring of 1919, the torgai group under the leadership of Akhmad Boytursunov belonging to the Alash Horde turned over to the side of the Soviet government, leading to the surrender of several Kazakh leaders led by M. Tinishboev. In particular, Jumakhan Kuderin, Sadiq Omonyolov, Bozorboy Mametov, Mirzakhan Tolaboev, Ollobergan Ummatboev, Bilol Suleev and others defected to the Soviet government in late 1919-early 1920 and saved their lives.

M. Tinishboev moved to Tashkent at the invitation of Turor Riskulov, the chairman of the Central Executive Committee of the Turkestan ASSR. During his 5-year career in Tashkent, he headed the Department of Water Management in the Ministry of Agriculture. He also teaches physics and mathematics at the Kazakh Institute of Public Education in Tashkent, and conducts research on ethnography and history.

In 1925, he returned to Kazakhstan and worked as the chief engineer of the new capital, Kyzylorda. In 1927-1930, he worked as a person responsible for the construction of the Turkestan-Siberian railway (Turksib).

No matter where M. Tinishboev works, he is always under the persecution of the OGPU. Such a situation will worsen with the imprisonment of several Kazakh elites led by Akhmed Boytursunov.

In 1930, he was imprisoned by OGPU agents as the "leader of Turkestan Autonomy and Alash State" and exiled to Central Chernozem (now Voronezh) region for 5 years. During his exile, he was involved in the construction of the Moscow-Donbass railway.

After the exile ends, he lives a normal life for a while. However, he was captured by NKVD agents on November 21, 1937, and shot at prison in 1938.

References:

1. SARF (State Archive of the Russian Federation), fund 101, list 112, case 18, sheets 75-100.
2. SASPHR (State Archive of Social and Political History of Russia), fund 75, list 33, case 1540, 33-45 - sheets.
3. Mukhammedjan Tinishbayev. Memories, documents, photography. -Almaty: 2017. -127.p